

THE IMPORTANCE OF DEVELOPING CULTURE OF COMMUNICATION TO FUTURE DESIGNERS

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Abstract. *The problem of the formation of communication, in particular its severity, is of particular importance as a priority for the qualification of specialists since the limitation and use by students of universal, humanistic and ethical aspects and their implementation, especially in communication, not only for the personal and spiritual development of a young person but in society and culture, professional, high specialists. This article denotes developing verbal communication in the educational process, which is significant in daily life. There are shown some effective techniques which you can use for developing students' communication skills.*

Keywords: *education, student, effective techniques, professional skills, communicative competence, competence, development, formation, process, manner, development, conversation.*

The interaction of a person with the world takes place in the system of objective relations between people formed in the course of their social life and production activities. In the process of production, people interact not only with nature but also with each other. Every part of our life requires the ability to communicate. Whether you're ordering a meal at a restaurant, answering interview questions, or apologizing to a friend, the ability to effectively and concisely express your thoughts and feelings is essential to a successful connection.

The influence of our national values and oriental upbringing is also felt in communication. In our country, the relationship with people, conversation, as well as communication-related to work and service is called dealing. The most beautiful deal is - a compliment. The greatest Uzbek scientist Alisher Navoi wrote that it is dealing-facing. So, in our nation, the ability to deal with people decently is understood as a sign of culture and nobility[3].

Nowadays, it is vital to create a democratic model of education. In education, especially the democratic model of the learning process the first element is manifested in the individual activity of the student. One of the components of personality development in higher education is the culture of student communication. The culture of communication between students at a university can be considered the most important creative resource of higher professional education in the intellectual development of the individual. The development of a culture of communication obliges a student of a higher educational institution to master it as a universal characteristic of a specialist, allowing him to fulfil the social expectations of society to a high professional and personal level. Higher education - is not only the sphere of education and upbringing of the young generation but also the most striking indicator of the spiritual, moral and social health of society, and the well-being of culture as a whole. The affirmation of humanistic values in education prioritizes the value of the individual and the depth of his spiritual world.

Communication -is a Greek word that means conversation, interpersonal conversation, and exchange of ideas, and it appears in the conversation of two or more people. In the process of communication, a person socializes and matures as a person under the influence of social experience, education, various relationships, moral standards, ideas and ideology. Interaction

between people is considered one of the main categories of pedagogical and psychological sciences, and it is; includes the most important mechanisms of interpersonal relations.

According to A.A. Leontiev, “Communication is a process or processes carried out within a certain social community - a group, a collective, society as a whole, processes in their essence, not interindividual, but social. They arise because of social need, and social necessity. Communication is what ensures collective activity[1,p.4].

A.L. Sventitsky distinguishes between verbal and non-verbal communication, arguing that: “Sometimes non-verbal communication even surpasses verbal forms in its effectiveness. Non-verbal communication involves the transfer of information without using the language of words. At the same time, we receive information through vision, fixing such expressive elements of behaviour as facial expression, gestures, posture, facial expressions, appearance in general” [2, p.242].

Communication in pedagogy means the competence, method and system of interaction of the learner and group of students, its essence, mutual information exchange, educational influence, and mutual understanding, is manifested and has the following characteristics:

- communication is the most important professional tool in the student's educational activity;
- social control and social laws are important to ensure proper implementation of the communication process;
- communication is considered the most important component of the relationship between the learner and the student, and it plays the same important role as the motive in motivation;
- communication in pedagogy is the active organization of interaction of the learner based on influencing the students, performing the planned function of implementing a specific goal based on the program;
- communication is a multifaceted process of development of interpersonal relations arising from the need for cooperation;

In the process of communication, the vital activity of a person and society is ensured, the structure and essence of social subjects change, historically specific types of personalities and the whole variety of human personalities are formed, a person is socialized, becoming a person.

Professionals with well-developed communication skills are in demand in all industries. The ability to communicate effectively helps to avoid misunderstandings and conflicts, find solutions to complex issues faster and work more productively. And this, in turn, saves the resources of companies. Therefore, communication skills are necessary for everyone, regardless of the field of activity, position and experience. After all, whether you work as a software developer or a sales manager, you need to be able to present your ideas to other people. In the labour market, design students make high competitiveness, so the future designer must have professional competencies. Students play a leading role in the practical lessons, and the teacher acts as an observer, which ultimately increases the practical value of the learning results. The modern designer is ready for self-education, and development of research qualities, manifest in the constant study of the theory design, psychology, materials technology, performance characteristics of products, marketing, consumption mechanisms, etc. It is important to focus on innovative research related to effective communication, with methods of creative activity, development of national culture, competitiveness and business. Interactive teaching methods are based on the principles where the role of the teacher is limited to directing the activities of students

to achieve certain learning goals and the implementation of step-by-step control in the course of training. The purpose of interactive learning is to create a comfortable learning environment in which the student feels his or her success, and intellectual and creative ability, which makes the whole process of learning, during which the necessary knowledge and skills for future professional activity of students - designers.

To achieve the goal of interactive learning of student-designer was developed a set of tasks:

- to interest the student in solving specific professional problems;
- to teach the ability to work in a team;
- to be tolerant of the opinion of others, to respect the right of everyone to freedom of speech,
- Respect the dignity of fellow students;
- to form a student's ability to argue his opinion and attitude to professional situations;
- reach the level of the student's informed professional competence.

In the educational process, it is effective for the teachers to use different models of techniques to form communication among students.

1. **“Socrates”** model. The teacher organizes active discussions, attracting the attention of the audience. Uniqueness in active discussion is based on individuality, creating an environment of constant intellectual competition, and the consistent desire of students to justify their point of view.

2. **Role-playing** is a classic way to teach communication skills. To use this technique, students demonstrate skills after discussion. For example, posture or body language. Psychologists communicate with people from 60% to 80% of the message that part comes from non-verbal means of expression and information found that only 20-40% are transmitted by oral route. Role-plays should always focus on full group participation and mutual respect. Making sure to talk to students about how to be respectful audience members and putting in a lot of time into daily role-playing to help students feel comfortable is required. Students should have patience and independent thinking, as well as positive relationships with each other. If we develop these skills first, role-playing can be a great way to quickly learn communication skills. Whenever I teach a new skill, I use role plays to check that students fully understand the information. Use specific scenarios that students experience every day in an office setting. After each role-play, we should discuss with the students what went well and what went wrong. They are required to ask what they can do to improve the situation.

3. **Group games** are an interactive, fun way to teach verbal and non-verbal communication, persuasion, cooperation and relationship-building skills. Through group games, students learn to effectively communicate information to others. During the games, the teacher should carefully monitor and take notes. Creating a group project Working as a group towards a specific goal requires communication. The team is asked to build, design or create something within a certain time. Provide the group with the necessary materials and monitor their interactions as they work. After that, the group should be asked questions about how it went. Observations are shared with positive comments about what they did well for everyone.

In conclusion, communication skills are the ability to communicate and receive information. And at first glance, it seems that there is nothing complicated about it. As children, we learnt to speak and understand others. But the essence here is not only in the exchange of information but also in the ability to express their thoughts as accurately as possible, to catch the

sense of words and adequately respond to other people's messages. All this is effective communication. The future designer must have a certain competence - it is not only the ability to assess his professional suitability but also the ability to communicate with people. Our task is to develop these abilities during the educational process.

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